

Federated Data Sharing and Analysis for Social Utility

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Status, Change History and Glossary

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Reviewed:	James Bowden	24/06/2024	James Bowden
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Table 1 Status Change History

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	01/04/2024	17	G. Terstyanszky	adding appendix 1 (templates to collect demonstrators' requirements) and appendix 2 (templates to collect cybersecurity Services' requirements)
	11/04/2024	19	G. Terstyanszky	creating chapter 2 and adding requirements of the Threat Intelligence demonstrator to chapter 2
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v.2	18/04/2024	21	A locovazzi	adding requirements of pattern recognition and image/video classification to chapter 2
	20/04/2024	23	G. Terstyanszky	creating chapter 3
	23/04/2024	26	J DesLaureriers	adding description of the UoW cloud resources
	01/05/2024	28	G. Terstyanszky	creating chapter 4 and describing how to use the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed
	06/05/2024		J. Bowden	specifying requirements of the Sleep Medicine demonstrators and describing the GWDG cloud resources
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Table 2 Deliverable Change History

ADT	Application Description Template
API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CBIT	Canary Bit AB
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
CPU	Central Processing Unit
EC2	Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud
GB	Giga Byte
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
KVM	Kernel-based Virtual Machine
MiCADO	Microservice-based Cloud Application-Level Orchestrator
ML	Machine Learning
RAM	Random Access Memory
UMG	Universitaets Medizin Goettingen
UoW	University of Westminster
VM	Virtual Machine

Table 3 List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

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Executive Summary

HARPOCRATES project investigates technologies, tools and solutions for secure and privacy-preserving data processing and sharing. The project has two demonstrators (Sleep Medicine and Threat Intelligence demonstrator) to validate the privacy preserving and security solutions developed in the project. The demonstrators are

- (i) exchange of sleep research data between three research institutions located in three EU member states (Finland, France and Germany) and
- (ii) exchange of threat intelligence information between two regional governments in EU member states (Italy and Spain).

In M06-M18 the Sleep Medicine demonstrator was extended with new functionality while the Threat Intelligence demonstrator was developed from scratch. By M18 neither of these demonstrators used any of the HARPOCRATES cybersecurity services that were under development in WP1 and WP4. The demonstrators will integrate some of these services with their application in M19-M36.

1 Introduction

The HARPOCRATES project aims to achieve ambitious objectives towards the long-term goal of enabling digitally blind processing of arbitrary data using complex processing functions. Achieving this long-term goal is a major undertaking with several initial activities that must be conducted, such as:

- **understanding** and documenting the constraints and limitations on the quality and structure of data to be processed;
- **contextualising** confidential data processing and sharing in terms of legal constraints and practical end-user requirements; and,
- **implementing** the cybersecurity services as cybersecurity services for confidential, privacy preserving and secure processing and sharing data and identifying its limitations and positioning the cybersecurity services along the current state of the art;
- **applying** the cybersecurity services in practical scenarios to demonstrate their practical use.

While the activities listed above have their specifics and prerequisites, they are connected in a logical roadmap that will be implemented in the HARPOCRATES project. One of the main expected outcomes of the project is developing novel cybersecurity algorithms and implementing these algorithms as cybersecurity services in the HARPOCRATES solution box. These services can be widely adapted and used in follow-up research and innovation actions, in commercial and industrial settings as well in education as educational tools.

1.1 Goals

This deliverable pursues three main goals that are relevant to stakeholders both internal and external to the project, as follows:

- **Inform** the reader about the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed.
- **Describe** the technical parameters of the cloud testbed.
- **Guide** project partners and external stakeholders in how to access and use the cloud testbed.
- **Give** an overview of developments of the Sleep Medicine and Threat Intelligence demonstrator made in M06-M18.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable contains 5 sections, including the “Introduction” section, and 3 appendices:

D4.1 Report on the Cloud Computing Testbed

- Section 2 “Requirements towards the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed” describes requirements of developers of HARPOCRATES demonstrators and cybersecurity services focusing on technical aspects.
- Section 3 “HARPOCRATES cloud testbed” outlines two academic clouds (GWDG and UoW) and one non-academic cloud (Amazon AWS) included and used in the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed.
- Section 4 “How to use the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed” describes how developers of the cybersecurity services and demonstrators can use the cloud testbed.
- Section 5 “HARPOCRATES demonstrators in M06-M18” outlines how the Sleep Medicine and Threat Intelligence demonstrator was developed in the first half of the project.
- Section 6 “Conclusions” gives a short summary of the HARPOCRATES testbed.
- Appendix 1 and 2 contain “Templates for requirements of the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed including requirements of demonstrators and cybersecurity services.
- Appendix 3 “Technical specifications of clouds of the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed”

2 Requirements towards the HARPOCRATES Cloud Testbed

There are two major user types of the HARPOCRATES testbed:

- developers of the HARPOCRATES demonstrator and
- developers of HARPOCRATES cybersecurity services.

T4.1 created templates to collect software, compute, storage and network requirements of developers of demonstrators and cybersecurity services. See the forms in Appendix 1 and Appendix 2. The task circulated these templates as both a Google Form and as a free-entry Microsoft Word document among the developers.

The task collected requirements from both the developers of the HARPOCRATES demonstrators and cybersecurity services to ensure that an appropriate set of cloud resources have been chosen for the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed. The requirements collected are four-fold: the software, compute, storage and network requirements of demonstrators and cybersecurity services. The collected requirements are presented in Table 2.1-2.4 (demonstrators) and in Table 2.5-2.8 (cybersecurity services) in the subsections below.

2.1 Demonstrators' Requirements towards the Cloud Testbed

T4.1 collected the requirements from the

- Sleep Medicine demonstrator and
- Threat Intelligence demonstrator.

Software requirements.

Demonstrators	Operating System Support	Application Language	External Dependencies	Licence Dependencies	Notes
Sleep Medicine	Linux	Java, Python, Matlab	Tomcat, PostgreSQL, NGINX, Docker	open source licences	
Threat intelligence	Linux and Windows	Python3.8	Python packages: feature-engine ==1.6.1 keras==2.13.1 Keras-Pre-processing ==1.1.2	open source - Linux not open source - Windows licence	

D4.1 Report on the Cloud Computing Testbed

			matplotlib==3.7.2 pandas==1.5.3 pickleshare==0.7.5 plotly==5.16.1 scikit-learn==1.3.1 scipy==1.10.1 tensorflow==2.13.0		
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Table 2.1 – Demonstrators’ Requirements – Software

Compute requirements.

Demonstrators	Nodes (VMs) required	CPU required for nodes	GPU support for nodes	RAM required for each node	Notes
Sleep Medicine	2	8	no	16GB	
Threat Intelligence	2 (1/organisation) 4 (1 per sub-organisation)	8	yes	32 GB	resource description used for current tests with users & monitored processes: 10 VENETO users 8 SARGA users 10 processes monitored

Table 2.2 – Demonstrators’ Requirements - Compute

Storage requirements.

Demonstrators	Storage hosted alongside the application	How much storage is required per node?	Notes
Sleep Medicine	2 TB	80 GB	80 GB of storage per node is the default provided by our CSP 2 TB external storage is for storing both encrypted and unencrypted copies of sleep datasets
Threat Intelligence	99 GB data of VENETO users in 4 months 152 GB data of SARGA in 8 months 1.2 GB SARGA trained models 855 M VENETO trained models	200GB per node □ 2 nodes (1 per organization) 100GB per node □ 4 nodes (1 per sub-organization)	estimation based on current data collecting rates

Table 2.3 – Demonstrators’ Requirements - Storage

Network requirements.

Demonstrators	Network requirements
Sleep Medicine	Configurable firewall
Threat Intelligence	Configurable firewall

Table 2.4 – Demonstrators’ Requirements - Networking

2.2 Requirements of cybersecurity services towards the Cloud Testbed

There are three HARPOCRATES cybersecurity services those development requires the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed:

- Functional Encryption service (FE),
- Homomorphic Encryption service (HE), and

- Pattern recognition and image/video classification service.

Software requirements.

Cybersecurity services	Operating System Support	Application Language	External Dependencies	Licence Dependencies	Notes
Functional Encryption services	Linux distribution, preferably Ubuntu	Rust, Python, C++	Miscellaneous dependencies to be installed on demand.	open source licences	Linux distribution, preferably Ubuntu
Homomorphic Encryption services	Linux (possibly CentOS or similar; or Ubuntu) Windows (tested with MSVC2017, MSVC2019) MacOS (gcc6+ upwards, NO CLANG)	C++ with cmake (needs g++) Python (3.7+) Cython on top of C++17	gRPC (included as external cmake dep, downloaded automatically and compiled)	open source licences	
Pattern recognition & image/video classification services	Linux distribution, preferably Ubuntu MacOS Big Sur+ Windows 10+	Python (version 3.10 is recommended for server)	Miscellaneous dependencies, to be installed on demand. Docker	open source licences	Linux distribution, preferably Ubuntu

Table 2.5 – Cybersecurity Services” Requirements – Software

Compute requirements:

Cybersecurity services	Nodes (VMs) required	CPU required for nodes	GPU support for nodes	RAM required for each node	Notes
Functional Encryption services	3 nodes	minimum 2 vCPU per node	none	16 GB	none
Homomorphic Encryption services	3 nodes are required, (to run a component instance: User, Analyst and CSP)	A compute optimised x86-64 multicore CPU	CUDA compatible GPU may be required later on	24 GB	1 st code is single-threaded. Parallel HHE transformation using multiple cores will be tested soon; eventually CUDA version may be also implemented and tested
Pattern recognition & image/video classification services	Three nodes	At least a compute optimised x86-64 multicore CPU	Better to have CUDA supported	16 GB	None

D4.1 Report on the Cloud Computing Testbed

	Minimum of 3 nodes	x86 CPU architecture, virtualization enabled	Not required initially		The hardware requirements of the node also depend on the algorithms that the node will run. less compute power for a descriptive statistical algorithm than for a machine learning model.
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Table 2.6 – Cybersecurity Services’ Requirements - Compute

Storage requirements:

Cybersecurity services	Storage hosted alongside the application	How much storage is required per node?	Notes
Functional Encryption services	64 GB	64 GB	
Homomorphic Encryption services			no particular storage requirements, data storage on the CSP components handled by UMG

Pattern recognition & image/video classification services	64 GB	64 GB	No extra storage requirements.
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Table 2.7 – Cybersecurity Services’ Requirements - Storage

Network requirements:

Cybersecurity services	Network requirements
Functional Encryption services	no any extra requirements
Homomorphic Encryption services	Significant bandwidth may be required to connect components running in the CSP, User and Analyst. The components need to communicate via gRPC for which one TCP port should be open to ingress traffic on the firewall that host them.
Pattern recognition & image/video classification services	no any extra requirements

Table 2.8 – Cybersecurity Services’ Requirements - Networking

2.3 Summary of requirements towards the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed

All developers, but the developers of the Threat Intelligence demonstrator, will use Linux to develop demonstrators and cybersecurity services. As a result, they will work in an open source environment. The developers of the Threat Intelligence demonstrator will use Windows. The developers will write C++, Java and Python code to elaborate demonstrator applications and cybersecurity services. The demonstrator applications and the cybersecurity services need between 2 and 3 cloud nodes. Some of these would require GPU support. See details in Table 2.2 and Table 2.6. The storage requirements on the cloud nodes are between 4 GB and 200 GB and between 20 GB and 2 TB for mid- and long-term storage. Neither demonstrator applications nor cybersecurity services, but Homomorphic Encryption service, have any extra network requirements. See details in Table 2.8.

3 HARPOCRATES Cloud Testbed

The aim of the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed is to provide the required hosting and execution environment to support the development, deployment and benchmarking of the HARPOCRATES demonstrators and cybersecurity services. The testbed contains three main building blocks:

- **Cloud deployments:** This represents the core cloud infrastructure to host the demonstrator applications and cybersecurity services. These can require both private (OpenStack) and public (AWS) cloud resources.
- **MiCADO - automated deployment and auto-scaling tool:** To facilitate the convenient deployment and portability of the demonstrator applications between multiple clouds, and to provide a cloud environment that is self-adaptive and automatically scales based on user defined policies, MiCADO¹ is used in the cloud testbed to orchestrate applications.
- **HARPOCRATES cybersecurity services:** The cloud testbed also supports the development of the HARPOCRATES cybersecurity services to create HARPOCRATES cybersecurity services that will be used by the HARPOCRATES demonstrators.

The cloud testbed incorporates resources from three cloud providers. There are resources offered from private clouds: UoW OpenStack cloud and GWDG cloud. The testbed also incorporates resources from Amazon AWS to allow developers to test their applications and solutions in a commercial environment.

3.1 Academic Clouds

3.1.1 GWDG Cloud

The “GWDG Cloud” is a service that is similar to known commercial cloud services offered by GWDG² However, it pays special attention to the needs of the scientific community. By using the “GWDG Cloud” web-based interfaces, developed by the GWDG, the user is able to independently create and manage server instances. Hereby the user chooses among a broad range of widespread Linux distributions as the base installation as well as different server flavours in terms of available processors and memory. For the realization of the service “GWDG Cloud” the GWDG consistently uses open source products such as OpenStack, KVM and Linux. All servers are running in the GWDG data centre on modern hardware in accordance with current data protection requirements.

¹ <https://micado-scale.eu/>

² <https://gwdg.de/>

In a first test phase, the IT officers of the Max Planck Institutes and the University of Göttingen evaluated the functions and made suggestions for optimization. The lessons learned were incorporated into the ongoing preparations for a public test phase in which the service “GWDG Cloud” was available to all members of the Max Planck Society and the University of Göttingen. Since completion of the test phase of the service “GWDG Cloud” it is now transferred to a production facility. As of June 2023, GWDG is successfully certified according to ISO 27001.

3.1.1.1 Access to GWDG Cloud

GWDG Cloud accounts are available to all researchers of Lower Saxony, Germany via the AcademicCloud³ single sign-on service. Any user with an academic cloud account can request a GWDG cloud service account. Resources are made available to these accounts by request to support.

Access to the graphical interface of the server is given directly via the web browser of the user whereby the server can be configured and more services are installed and managed. In order to enable accessibility of the servers on the Internet, public ip addresses can be assigned to the servers in a flexible way. Security settings allow the user also to define the rights (firewall) to make the server accessible from outside.

3.1.2 UoW OpenStack Cloud

The University of Westminster operates an IaaS (Infrastructure-as-a-Service) private cloud computing cluster intended for research and teaching. The cluster is an OpenStack Juno based infrastructure. The underlying software is based on LibVirt as the virtualising API and KVM as the hypervisor technology. This technology has been proven to be stable for several years and has become one of the virtualisation standards in both industry and the academic sector. The management works with the concept of tenants or projects. Defined by the cloud administrator, each tenant can use a defined number of resources set by the administrator. These resources include a number of CPUs, GB of RAM memory, disk space and Public IPs. Users manage the cloud resources either via EC2 and S3 APIs (Amazon compatible), the Nova API or the Horizon web interface.

Security is based on security groups that isolate the cloud instances (virtual machines running) from each other based on the users and/or projects they belong to. Inside each project, users can also define their own firewall rules and as many security rules as the administrator has allowed for them. Since the OpenStack cluster is running on the

³ <https://academiccloud.de>

University's internal network, there are strict firewall rules in place that drop all incoming connections on all ports. This can be configured on a per-instance basis to allow external connections on certain ports, for example, to provide SSH access or access to the MiCADO Dashboard.

Computer force is based on 28 Dell C6105 doing a total of:

- 248 CPUs (AMD Opteron 4122 Processor (2.2GHz, 4C, 4x512K L2/6M L3 Cache, 75W ACP), DDR3 -1333MHz).
- 2376GB RAM memory (Dual Rank LV RDIMMs 1333MHz)

Storage is based on:

- 5 TB RAID1 based, local storage, 40 x (SATA 7.2k 2.5" HD Hot Plug)
- 12 TB RAID1 based, (PowerVault MD3620i External 10Gb iSCSI + PowerVault MD1220 Base extension)
- Huawei OceanStor 5500 (18 x 550GB SSD + 24 x 3 TB NL-SAS disks), replicated to Huawei OceanStor 5300 (24 x 3 TB NL-SAS disks)

Networking is based on:

- PowerConnect 8024F 10GbE optical fibre switches for VLAN and storage connectivity.
- Standard 100M ethernet switches for administration and live migration purposes.

3.1.2.1 Access to the UoW cloud:

Early access to the UoW cloud resources was provided to the HARPOCRATES demonstrators in the form of pre-provisioned compute nodes of the required specification. Access to these nodes was granted via SSH, so the use-case is expected to provide a valid public key to authenticate against. The firewall will be configured on a per-instance basis to allow SSH access from outside the UoW network. Developers are given sudoer privileges so as to have full permissions for deploying and configuring a first test of the application on this cloud.

When MiCADO is introduced at the application level, MiCADO takes the role of provisioning and configuration of compute nodes at the infrastructure layer. To do so, MiCADO requires OpenStack credentials of a tenant able to provision resources within the project. The cloud orchestrators can then authenticate with and call the OpenStack API to create, destroy and configure virtual machines. Developers will be given access to the MiCADO API and MiCADO Dashboard, and SSH access to nodes could be granted for debugging purposes.

Direct access to the OpenStack Web UI can be extended to any project members who wish to provision and manage the above cloud compute nodes for the use cases.

Remark. UoW set up and provided the OpenStack based cloud resources for the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed but it was flooded and currently it is not available. UoW technical staff is working on restoring these cloud resources.

3.2 Non-academic Clouds

3.2.1 Amazon AWS EC2

The University of Westminster holds a provision on Amazon Web Services (AWS). AWS operates a large number of public cloud services ranging from traditional cloud offerings such as compute and storage, to support for more recent workloads such as machine learning and IoT. The Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2) service is the main IaaS offering from AWS and supports provisioning CPU and GPU instances of various Linux flavours and sizes. The hypervisor varies depending on the instance family, but these are generally customisations based on KVM. Storage is offered by the S3 (object storage) and EBS (block storage) services, which are both well integrated with EC2. The S3 and EC2 APIs are extensively documented and extensively used. The EC2 service is an extremely popular choice in public clouds but can also be found underpinning private clouds such as OpenNebula and offering compatibility with open projects such as OpenStack. Interacting with AWS EC2 is done via CloudFormation templates (proprietary Infrastructure-as-Code), the EC2 APIs, or the web interface. Both cloud orchestrators in MiCADO support AWS and they require access key and secret key credentials from a programmatic user defined in the AWS Identity & Access Management service.

CBIT uses an AWS-based infrastructure for development and testing of its privacy-preserving federated learning cybersecurity services. In M16-M18 CBIT used only a minimal set of resources for development (1 free-tier VM). In the remaining period during the project, CBIT will use more nodes (3 VMs with at least 2vCPUs each). These resources will be used to test CBIT's privacy-preserving federated learning cybersecurity service with more data, as well as deploy the ancillary services necessary to support the HARPOCRATES toolbox according to the architecture described in D3.1.

3.2.1.1 Access to the Amazon EC2 cloud:

Access of HARPOCRATES demonstrators and cybersecurity services to EC2 primarily is through a single MiCADO Master machine. Both demonstrators and cybersecurity services have access to the MiCADO API to deploy their applications and to the MiCADO Dashboard

to monitor them. For special cases, bare Linux VMs could be provisioned, and access granted to the use-cases via SSH. Full user access to AWS is currently restricted to project members managing the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed at UoW.

3.3 Docker Container Registry

Containers offer lightweight virtualisation for packaging and shipping software and are fast becoming standard in software engineering. MiCADO currently supports Docker⁴ containers built from Docker container images, which can be stored in public or private Docker registries. MiCADO supports public registries such as the official public DockerHub, as well as private registries, which can be self-hosted, managed by a cloud provider, or subscribed to on the private DockerHub.

For open-source projects, the public DockerHub is usually sufficient, however, a private registry can be useful during the development phase. When working from within a private cloud with strict firewall rules, an internally hosted private registry can also be very beneficial for ease of access to container images. MiCADO and the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed are able to support both the official public and private DockerHub, and resources have been set aside within the testbed to self-host a private registry within the University of Westminster cloud on an as-needed basis.

⁴ <https://docker.com>

4 How to Use the HARPOCRATES Cloud Testbed

To demonstrate the applicability and efficiency of the HARPOCRATES cybersecurity services developed in the HARPOCRATES project, HARPOCRATES demonstrators can use them across either a single or multiple cloud service provider platforms. MiCADO might facilitate this by providing an abstraction layer on top of the cloud testbed infrastructure if it is required by any of the HARPOCRATES demonstrators. It runs the deployment and runtime orchestration of demonstrator applications integrated with some of HARPOCRATES cybersecurity services.

The TOSCA based ADT (Application Description Template) used to describe applications for MiCADO. TOSCA is an OASIS Standard for describing cloud applications which pays special attention to ensuring both portability across cloud platforms, and reusability of previous templates. The various components of an application's deployment can be described individually, for example the Sleep Medicine demonstrator application, HARPOCRATES cybersecurity services, etc. and the compute and storage infrastructure in the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed. These descriptions can be assembled into different ADTs, each describing the complete application infrastructure for the HARPOCRATES demonstrator, the set of HARPOCRATES cybersecurity services required for the demonstrator, the specific testbed resources from the chosen cloud service provider, and the desired set of policies for the deployment and execution. Submitting the completed ADT, MiCADO automatically provides the needed cloud resources, deploys the application and cybersecurity security, and enforces the necessary set of policies.

An ADT can be modified to select a different cloud service provider from within the cloud testbed or extended adding either another or upgraded HARPOCRATES cybersecurity services. This approach makes testing across platforms simple and straightforward. This also facilitates agile development of the HARPOCRATES demonstrator and cybersecurity services.

4.1 Selection of Cloud Service Providers

The HARPOCRATES cloud testbed is formed of three different clouds to provide a good cross-section of the available offerings on the market today. Resources of both private (UoW and GWDG cloud) and public (AWS cloud) clouds can be accessed. Both OpenStack and EC2 underlie a multitude of private and smaller commercial clouds, and their APIs and interfaces are fast becoming standard in the industry.

D4.1 Report on the Cloud Computing Testbed

The UoW OpenStack cloud is a private cloud hosted on-premise at the University of Westminster. It serves as the primary cloud resource within the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed. It is administered by UoW staff and managed in T4.1 by the UoW team, and being on-premise, has no on-demand pricing associated with it, making it the most flexible resource within the testbed. A strict deep packet inspection firewall at the University offers very high levels of security, though sometimes to the detriment of network speed, and connectivity with external services and endpoints.

The GWDG cloud is also a private cloud that forms part of the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed solely to support the Sleep Medicine demonstrator. As the demonstrator processes sleep data its privacy and security at the infrastructure level are of the highest importance. The GWDG cloud is administered and operated by GWDG, who are a joint institution of the University of Göttingen and the Max Planck Society, offering complete control over the resources running within it and making it the best option for deploying and executing this demonstrator.

The AWS EC2 cloud offers a high network throughput and open connectivity with external services, making it an excellent resource for best scenario benchmarking and demonstrations of HARPOCRATES services alongside each demonstrator. EC2 also offers a greater range of compute instances and storage solutions than does the UoW cloud, including access to GPU-powered instances which will be a requirement for at least one of the demonstrators.

Each of the three cloud platforms that make up the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed have their own advantages and together they are well suited to supporting the specific user requirements of the two HARPOCRATES demonstrators, as well as needs of the HARPOCRATES cybersecurity services.

5 HARPOCRATES Demonstrators in M06-M18

In this section the project partners who are behind the HARPOCRATES demonstrators describe the developments of the demonstrator applications in M06-M18, their current status and developments planned for M19-M36. In M06-M18 the efforts focused on the development and customisation of the demonstrator applications to make them suitable for prototyping the HARPOCRATES cybersecurity services. However, none of these services have been integrated into the demonstrators according to the schedule presented in the Grant Agreement.

First, a short overview is given that explains the background and motivation behind the application. Next, the development and research activities of the demonstrators, carried out in M06-M18, is described. Finally, how the HARPOCRATES cybersecurity services will be integrated and applied to enhance the security of both demonstrators is explained.

5.1 Sleep Medicine Demonstrator - Collaborative use of Machine Learning in Sleep Medicine

5.1.1 Background and Motivation

Partners. Three Sleep Medicine centres from three different countries (Charite University Hospital in Germany, Kuopio University Hospital in Finland and Hospital de Dieu from France) are involved in this demonstrator. The technical development of the demonstrator is supported by the Medical Informatics team from the University Hospital of Göttingen Germany.

Problem Description. Machine and deep learning-related research have gained great interest during the last years in Sleep Medicine. Research utilising these methods need to exploit a huge amount of clinically sensitive data. This raises several issues, such as the openness of research, concerns of patient privacy, data security and how to find balance between these issues. Currently, research in Sleep Medicine is supposed to follow the FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and the recent European Commission's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, 2016/679). However, following the GDPR hinders implementation of FAIR principles and makes data sharing between clinical or research institutions highly difficult, especially in the case of retrospective data.

Data sharing should contain three steps: (1) data encryption, (2) data sharing with secured platforms, and (3) secure data storage. However, data encryption has not received the attention it deserves albeit being one of the key elements since if for any reason the two

other steps fail, data encryption still ensures that the data is protected and patient identification is not possible. Thus, *having sophisticated and validated data encryption algorithms* would be highly valuable for both the clinical and research community. Additionally, performing complex analytics and Machine Learning operations on the encrypted data can facilitate the joint exploitation of sleep data.

Planned demonstrator application. The demonstrator will utilise data consisting of *sleep recordings* (i.e., electroencephalography, electrooculography, electromyography, breathing signals, oximetry signals, snoring (audio), sleeping position, respiratory effort, and possibly the nocturnal video recording), *patient medical records* and *questionnaires* related to sleep disorders in text format (word, excel, etc.).

The aim of the demonstrator is to illustrate that after the encryption the sleep recordings can be handled and analysed similarly (using complex analytics and ML techniques) to the non-encrypted data. It is necessary that the solution can be used regardless of the sleep recording device and software used to collect and/or analyse the data. Encryption should be possible also regardless of the number or quality of signals in sleep recordings. The solution should also include a user-friendly user interface and be readily usable in the clinical (operational) environment by clinical practitioners.

5.1.2 Application Development and Deployment in M06-M18

In M01-M18 development of the Sleep Medicine demonstrator has focused on two aspects:

- 1) Developing and deploying the data management and data processing infrastructure.
- 2) Designing a proof of concept Machine Learning model that is compatible with the HARPOCRATES PPML HHE cybersecurity service.

The data management and data processing infrastructure. It was deployed on the GWDG cloud platform (See details in Section 3.1.1). This infrastructure is built on open source services and provides storage, access control and workflow management for biomedical data. It is highly extensible and offers a number of interfaces for integrating with other software and services. This platform will be used as a testbed for integrating and evaluating the cybersecurity services of the HARPOCRATES toolbox. Figure 5.1 shows a component view of the infrastructure. Each component of this platform is described in Table 5.1.

Figure 5.1 – Component view of the demonstrator data management and processing infrastructure

Component	Description
XNAT ⁵	An open source biomedical data management application that provides storage and access control for biomedical and clinical data. Additionally, it provides workflow management for data processing tasks
Docker ⁶	An OS-Level visualisation runtime for running containerized algorithms for data processing
PostgreSQL ⁷	A relational database, required by XNAT and used to store metadata and data access permissions
Ceph ⁸	A Ceph Storage Cluster operated by GWDG that provides object storage and block storage,
Keycloak ⁹	An identity provider. provided by Academic Cloud ¹⁰ , it allows users of Academic Cloud to register with the services using their existing credentials

⁵ <https://xnat.org/>

⁶ <https://www.docker.com/>

⁷ <https://www.postgresql.org/>

⁸ <https://ceph.io/>

⁹ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

¹⁰ <https://academiccloud.de/>

Exchange ¹¹	An email service provided by GWDG for sending messages to users
UI	End user interface application. Either the XNAT web application interface or some external application using the XNAT HTTPS API.

Table 5.1 – Components of the data management and data processing infrastructure

Proof of concept Machine Learning model. It was created to detect the presence of desaturation events in short segments of SpO2 data, as described in D3.1. This model was trained and evaluated on the SIESTA dataset. The goal was to build a model that would be compatible with the distributed HHE implementation available in the HARPOCRATES toolbox. Considering the HHE implementation, the model should be a simple single hidden layer model with only 10 hidden nodes. This also required preprocessing the SIESTA dataset and scaling the SpO2 signal values 5 bit integers. This model provided 87-90% binary classification accuracy on the non-encrypted data. Finally the model was deployed to the data management and processing infrastructure. This allows the evaluation of the accuracy of the model on other datasets and will eventually allow the evaluation of the HARPOCRATES PPML HHE cybersecurity service against the plain text solution in real world medical informatics environment

5.1.3 Plans for Extending the Sleep Medicine Demonstrator with HARPOCRATES Cybersecurity Services in M19-M36

In D3.1 a number of potential data analysis tasks were described. Collaboration with the technical work packages revealed only two of them to be feasible at this time due to implementation limitations of the cybersecurity services' in the HARPOCRATES toolbox. These tasks and their target cybersecurity services are presented in Table 5.2.

Task	Cybersecurity services	Its implementation
Estimation of presence of desaturations in short segments of SpO2	PPML HHE	https://github.com/harpocrates-project/distributed_hhe_ppml
Calculation of sleep fragmentation from hypnograms	PPML FE	https://github.com/harpocrates-project/SPADE

Table 5.2 – Data analysis tasks of the Sleep Medicine demonstrator

¹¹ <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoft-365/exchange/email/>

At this stage the implementations are in early development. Using the currently released source code and documentation, some potential use cases have been designed and are presented below. At this time these use cases are limited to the PPML HHE cybersecurity service, as the PPML FE cybersecurity service was only recently released. Work will continue on the design of the PPML FE use cases and the technical work packages will be monitored in case of a major breakthrough that allows us to attempt more complex tasks.

Estimation of presence of desaturations in short segments of SpO2 for research. The PPML HHE cybersecurity service will be demonstrated for research purposes. The plaintext approach to desaturation detection will be compared to the HHE approach, and the encrypted approach will be evaluated on multiple datasets. A proof of concept workflow will also be implemented where multiple sleep centres will share data and models in a privacy preserving way for the purpose of research.

- Researchers provide model
- Clinic provides data
- CSP provides compute resources
- Researchers can ask:
 - What is the accuracy of the model compared to the plaintext approach?
 - What is the accuracy of the model on other data?
 - Research metrics, eg: How many patients have a desaturation event at least every hour?

Figure 5.2 – Sequence diagram showing a preliminary protocol design the privacy preserving estimation of presence of desaturations in short segments of SpO2 for research purposes with HHE

Estimation of presence of desaturations in short segments of SpO2 for diagnostics.

The PPML HHE cybersecurity service will be also demonstrated for diagnostic purposes. A proof of concept workflow will be implemented where multiple sleep centres will share data and models in a privacy preserving way for the purpose of diagnostics.

- Clinic provides model
- Patient (or outpatient centre) provides data
- CSP provides compute resources
- Clinic can ask:
 - Does this patient have desaturation events?
 - Does this patient have a desaturation event at least every hour?

Figure 5.3 – Sequence diagram showing a preliminary protocol design for the privacy preserving estimation of presence of desaturations in short segments of SpO2 for diagnostic purposes with HHE

5.2 Threat Intelligence Demonstrator - Identifying unexpected behaviours in computers

5.2.1 Background and Motivation

Partners. Two local authorities, Sociedad Aragonesa de Gestión Agroambiental (SARGA), in Aragón, Spain, and Regione del Veneto (VENETO), in Veneto, Italy, and a cybersecurity company, S2 Grupo (S2G), in Spain, are involved in this demonstrator. Cybersecurity experts and AI experts in S2G provide cybersecurity and technical expertise for developing the demonstrator application.

Problem description. Local authorities provide important services, such as health, education, social services, etc. for citizens. These services could be exposed to great risks because they could be targeted by cyber attacks. The Threat Intelligence demonstrator aims at detecting Advanced Persistent Threats^{12,13} (APTs). These are intelligent attacks which are usually tailored to the target organisation or person. They are undetectable by

¹² <https://www.kaspersky.com/resource-center/definitions/advanced-persistent-threats>

¹³ <https://www.trendmicro.com/vinfo/us/security/definition/advanced-persistent-threat>

signature-based tools like, for instance, detection rules. One of the best ways to detect, or even prevent, such attacks is by being alert to any unexpected behaviour in the system. ML algorithms for anomaly detection are commonly used in order to learn the normal behaviour of the system, user or entity and then raising an alarm whenever the observed behaviour does not correspond to one predicted by the trained ML model.

This anomaly detection approach for threat detection is very useful but it also has limitations. For instance, when the amount of information to be processed by the model is too high, even a model considering as normal activity 99.5% of all the observed activity and marking as suspicious the 0.5% of the activity, can result in too many alerts to be inspected by a human cybersecurity expert. Also, most of these models consider as anomalies those activities which are significantly less common than the most of other activities. However, less common behaviours are not always malicious. For instance, installing a driver or an update in a computer is something that most users do but, since it is less common than 0.5% of the actions a user does, it would be marked as an anomalous activity. Also, malicious activity is not always spurious. In the case of DoS¹⁴ or DDoS¹⁵ attacks, malicious activity takes place frequently in a small time lapse and thus, depending on the amount of time which is being used to estimate what is normal and what is not normal in a system, these attacks could be considered as normal activity.

An important limitation that these models have, which is directly related to the HARPOCRATES project, is that, as most ML models, anomaly detection models usually require big amounts of data covering most (if not all) possible situations to learn what is normal in a system or entity. In these demonstrator, the behaviour of a system is characterised by attending to the behaviour of processes running in it.

The two local authorities in Aragon, Spain and Veneto, Italy will track users' activities using the Windows Sysmon tool¹⁶. This tool compiles logs from the activity of each process running in the different computers while users are doing their normal work. Each process activity is tracked in terms of which folders or files it creates or accesses, which other processes creates, priority level escalation, network connection, etc. This activity log of each process will be used for modelling the normal behaviour of well-known processes, such as winword.exe, chrome.exe, cmd.exe, lsass.exe, etc. This activity log of each process will be used for modelling the normal behaviour of well-known processes, such as winword.exe, chrome.exe, cmd.exe, lsass.exe, etc. In order to do such modelling separated ML models will

¹⁴ <https://www.trendmicro.com/vinfo/us/security/definition/denial-of-service-dos>

¹⁵ <https://www.trendmicro.com/vinfo/us/security/definition/distributed-denial-of-service>

¹⁶ <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/sysinternals/downloads/sysmon>

be trained for each process. In this way, once individual models are trained, it will be possible to detect when a well-known process is behaving in an unexpected, suspicious way. In order to be able to train the above-mentioned ML models, both organisations will track various users' activity and build a dataset that will be shared and jointly exploited.

5.2.2 Application Development and Deployment in M06-M18

In M06-M18 development of the Threat Intelligence demonstrator has focused on the following aspects:

1. Recruiting first volunteers to serve as data providers for the demonstrator.
2. Developing and deploying the data management and data processing infrastructure.
3. Designing a proof of concept Machine Learning model that is compatible with Privacy Preserving capabilities developed in HARPOCRATES.
4. Designing a set of experiments for testing and validating Privacy Preserving capabilities developed in HARPOCRATES.

Recruiting first volunteers to serve as data providers for the demonstrator.

SARGA and VENETO elaborated a strategy to recruit users to volunteer as data providers for the Threat Intelligence demonstrator. Having this strategy, they approached employees at the Aragon and the Veneto local authority to be data providers and recruited the first data providers to get involved in testing the application of the Threat Intelligence demonstrator.

Developing and deploying the data management and data processing infrastructure.

Figure 5.4 shows the architecture of the Threat Intelligence demonstrator. S2G deployed a log extractor agent in the computers of SARGA and VENETO volunteers and started gathering their data. This data is preprocessed in two phases by S2G before sharing it with the rest of the HARPOCRATES consortium:

- In the first phase raw logs are normalised and anonymized substituting all references to specific user names by the string 'user_name', substituting paths to system directories with reserved keywords, etc. The normalised and anonymized is in text format
- In the second phase normalised and anonymized data is converted to a numeric format, mostly categorical values.

After completing the second phase the data is suitable for training ML models. HARPOCRATES partners developing the cybersecurity services are also provided with data after the first phase for getting better understanding of data when validating experiments.

Raw logs are kept by S2G for an agreed period of time, just in case there was any error in the preprocessing which might require that raw data to be processed again.

Figure 5.4 – Data gathering and pre processing and ML model training in the Threat Intelligence demonstrator

Designing a proof of concept Machine Learning model that is compatible with Privacy Preserving capabilities developed in HARPOCRATES

As above mentioned, the Threat Intelligence demonstrator aims at detecting Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs) by training different anomaly detection ML models to learn the normal behaviour of processes running in a Windows operating system and raising an alarm when a process is not behaving as previously observed. It is not feasible to train a different model for each potential process executed in a computer. Further, it is unfeasible to train a single model to learn the normal behaviour of all potential processes running in a system. Considering these constraints, partners involved in the Threat Intelligence demonstrator narrowed down a list of well-known processes which were commonly used by different users in different organisations. For each of the processes, a ML model will be trained to learn the normal behaviour of that process in a group of users. As a result, unexpected behaviour (behaviour beyond a specific anomaly threshold, set at training time) will be considered as an Indicator of Compromise (IoC). The list of selected processes to take part in the validation experiments is in Table 5.3.

Process name	Type (Operating System/User)
cmd.exe	Operating System

Process name	Type (Operating System/User)
csc.exe	Operating System
cvtres.exe	Operating System
excel.exe	User
explorer.exe	Operating System
powershell.exe	Operating System
rundll32.exe	Operating System
seVICES.exe	Operating System
sysmon.exe	Operating System
winword.exe	User

Table 5.3 – List of processes selected for validation

As it can be observed, some of these processes, such as explorer.exe, are included in the Windows Operating System, while others, like winword.exe, are installed by users. The criteria to select processes considered a subset of processes which were common in both organisations and which were commonly used by APT groups to attack the system. In this way, it would be possible to inject actions part of already known APT attacks in uninfected logs to serve as attacks. Some of these processes imply more interaction with the user (for instance, winword.exe, cmd.exe), while others just run in background without the user noticing them (for instance, rundll32.exe). This can result in a higher variability of the behaviour observed in some processes which may impact detection rates with and without PET developed in HARPOCRATES.

This demonstrator will make use of Federated Learning capabilities developed in HARPOCRATES so that local ML models can be trained in each organisation and later combined to obtain a stronger trained model suitable for both organisations.

In order to prevent the system from any adversarial attack, locally trained models are encrypted using the HHE capabilities developed in HARPOCRATES. To prevent model inference due to having only two organisations, volunteers in each organisation will be split

in two sub organisations, simulating a scenario in which 4 organisations take part and share their trained models. This casuistic will be considered when designing validation experiments for this demonstrator.

S2G, SARGA and VENETO collaborated in the development of anomalous behaviour detection ML models for the different well-known processes (as earlier explained). These anonymized and normalised datasets, as well as the initial demonstrator will be shared with the rest of the consortium to be used in the demonstrator. A subset of the normalised dataset will be used for testing. In order to do so, malicious and anomalous activity will be injected by S2 in the testing subset.

Designing a set of experiments for testing and validating Privacy Preserving capabilities developed in HARPOCRATES

In order to design a set of experiments for the final validation of HARPOCRATES' cybersecurity services to assess their impact on the demonstrator, S2G carried out a preliminary analysis of SARGA and VENETO users attending to the processes they run and to the behaviour of these processes for each of them. Figures 5.5 and 5.6 show these results involving the first SARGA and VENETO volunteers.

Figure 5.5 – Representation of the first SARGA volunteers' behaviour

As it can be observed, SARGA users are classified in five different groups. SARGA confirmed that these differences make sense attending to the different job positions of the volunteers, but it is probable that this classification changes when more volunteers take part in the experiment. In any case, preliminary experiments were done attending to this classification.

Figure 5.6 shows the clustering of users of both organisations, which has also been used for experiments using volunteers of both organisations.

After this preliminary study, it was decided to consider differences among users in any organisation. For instance, users working in a sales department probably don't run the same programs as programmers or network administrators. Training ML models with specific users or with a balanced set of volunteers may impact final detection results, both with and without PET developed in HARPOCRATES. In order to measure these differences among users, a clustering attending to the behaviour of the logged processes was made. The figure 5.6 shows results of this clustering for current SARGA volunteers.

Figure 5.6 – Representation of first volunteers's behaviour at both SARGA and VENETO

The use cases considered for experimentation and validation of developments within the project are presented in Table 5.4:

ID	Short Name	Train	Test	Description	Results	
					WO/HA	WI/HA
0	BULK TEST	ALL	ALL	<p>Train and test are carried out with all available users from both organisations.</p> <p>Objective: Measuring differences in the use case with and without HARPOCRATES</p>		

ID	Short Name	Train	Test	Description	Results	
					WO/HA	WI/HA
				developments.		
1	ORG_TEST_SA	SARGA	SARGA	Similar to BULK_TEST, but train and test are carried out separately for each organisation.		
2	ORG_TEST_VE	VENETO	VENETO			
3	SPLIT_SMLR_SA	SARGA1	SARGA2	SARGA users are split into two groups as homogeneous as possible, attending to the clustering process above mentioned. Train is carried out using data from one of the groups and models are tested against the other group.		
4	SPLIT_SMLR_VE	VENETO1	VENETO2	Equivalent to SPLIT_SMLR_SA but with VENETO users.		
5	SPLIT_DIFF_SA	SARGA1	SARGA2	SARGA users are split into two groups which are different from each other, attending to the clustering process mentioned above. Train is carried out using data from one of the groups and models are tested against the other group.		
6	SPLIT_DIFF_VE	VENETO1	VENETO2	Equivalent to SPLIT_DIFF_SA but with VENETO users.		
7	CROSSED_SA2VE	SARGA	VENETO	Models trained using data from all SARGA users and tested against data of VENETO users.		
8	CROSSED_VE2SA	VENETO	SARGA	Models trained using data from all VENETO users and tested against data of SARGA users.		

ID	Short Name	Train	Test	Description	Results	
					WO/HA	WI/HA
9	CROSSED_SA2VE_SMLR	SARGA1	VENETO1	Models trained using data from a subset of SARGA users and tested against data of a subset of VENETO users. Both subsets of users, SARGA1 and VENETO1, are built picking users which are as similar among them as possible, attending to the clustering process mentioned above.		
10	CROSSED_VE2SA_SMLR	VENETO1	SARGA1	Models trained using data from a subset of SARGA users and tested against data of a subset of VENETO users. Both subsets of users are built picking users so that VENETO1 and SARGA1 are as similar as possible, attending to the clustering process mentioned above.		
11	CROSSED_SA2VE_DIF	SARGA1	VENETO1	Models trained using data from a subset of SARGA users and tested against data of a subset of VENETO users. Both subsets of users are built picking users so that users in VENETO1 are different from those in SARGA1, attending to the clustering process mentioned above.		
12	CROSSED_VE2SA_DIF	VENETO1	SARGA1	Models trained using data from a subset of VENETO users and tested against data of a subset of SARGA users. Both subsets of users are built picking users so that users in VENETO1 are different from those in SARGA1, attending to the clustering process mentioned above.		

Table 5.4 – Use cases considered for validation of the Threat Intelligence demonstrator

5.2.3 Plans for Extending the Demonstrator with HARPOCRATES Cybersecurity Services in M19-M36

Currently the threat detection capabilities in this demonstrator have been developed and tested without HARPOCRATES' PET developments. Next months the final users (S2G, SARGA and VENETO) will work together with technical partners to include FML and HE tools in the demonstrator and will start validating results. For the validation, different aspects will be considered: Not only the potential impact on threat detection rates, but also impact in the number of data necessary to train valid models and the necessary time to obtain them.

DRAFT

6 Conclusion and Future Works

This deliverable gives an overview of the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed. It is crucial for the development, deployment and benchmarking of the HARPOCRATES demonstrators and cybersecurity services to showcase how the technical solutions developed in the project can be utilised in several user scenarios. The testbed has now been established and fully operational.

To create the testbed first, T4.1 collected the technical requirements of the HARPOCRATES demonstrators and cybersecurity services. It was followed by the selection and definition of cloud computing resources and the scalable microservices-based deployment and run-time management framework (MiCADO).

As the cloud testbed is now fully operational, future work is two-folded. First, the operation of the testbed will be assured by continuous maintenance and user support. Second, the testbed will be further developed and extended based on the specific requirements of the demonstrator applications and cybersecurity services. UoW will work on further developing the MiCADO framework in order to fully support the automated deployment, autoscaling and portability of the HARPOCRATES demonstrators.

T4.2 extended the application of the Sleep Medicine demonstrator and developed from scratch the application of the Threat Intelligence demonstrator in M06-M18. As a result, these applications offer the functionality required for analyzing non-encrypted sleep data and identifying unexpected events in user behaviour. Partners involved in the development of these applications identified cybersecurity services in the HARPOCRATES toolbox they will integrate with the applications in M19-M36.

Appendix 1 – Templates for collecting requirements of the HARPOCRATES demonstrators

Software requirements

Demonstrators	Operating System Support	Application Language	External Dependencies	Licence Dependencies
Sleep Medicine				
Threat intelligence				

Compute requirements

Demonstrators	Nodes (virtual machine) required	CPU required for nodes	GPU support for nodes	RAM required for each node	Notes
Sleep Medicine					
Threat Intelligence					

Storage requirements

Demonstrators	Storage hosted alongside the application	How much storage is required per node?	Notes
Sleep Medicine			
Threat Intelligence			

Network requirements

Demonstrators	Additional Info
Sleep Medicine	
Threat Intelligence	

Appendix 2 – Templates for collecting requirements of the HARPOCRATES cybersecurity services

Software requirements

Cybersecurity services	Operating System	Application Language	External Dependencies	Licence Dependencies
Functional Encryption				
Homomorphic Encryption				
Pattern recognition & image/video classification				

Compute requirements

Cybersecurity services	Nodes (virtual machine) required	CPU required for nodes	GPU support for nodes	RAM required for each node	Notes
Functional Encryption					
Homomorphic Encryption					
Pattern recognition & image/video classification					

Storage requirements

Cybersecurity services	Storage hosted alongside the application	How much storage is required per node?	Notes
Functional Encryption			
Homomorphic Encryption			
Pattern recognition & image/video classification			

Network requirements

Cybersecurity services	Additional Info
Functional Encryption	
Homomorphic Encryption	
Pattern recognition & image/video classification	

Appendix 3 - Technical Specifications of Clouds of the HARPOCRATES cloud testbed

UoW Cloud	
General Configuration	
Description	Private OpenStack cloud at University of Westminster
Hypervisor	KVM
IaaS Service	OpenStack Juno
Monitoring	none
Access Methods	Nova API, Web Interface, EC2/S3 (Amazon compatible)
Connectivity	Strict - deep packet inspection firewall
Cloud-Interface	
Provisioning	Web UI, MiCADO, Nova API
Cloud Integration	cloud-init, OpenStack HEAT, EC2
Networking	Web Console, API
MiCADO Integration	Integrated
Storage	
Interfaces	Swift (object), Cinder (block)
Image Format	QCOW2, RAW
SSD Capacity	-
HDD Capacity	2000GB
Quota	None
Compute	
CPU (GHz/core)	160 CPUs
CPU Quota	100 CPUs
RAM (GB/VM)	62.9GB
RAM Quota	100GB
VM Quota	50
Linux Provision Time	Slow (3min+)
Win. Provision Time	-
Networking	
Internal bandwidth	20GB per VM
External bandwidth	20GB per VM
Inter-VM latency	1ms

GWDG Cloud	
General Configuration	
Description	Private OpenStack cloud at GWDG
Hypervisor	KVM
IaaS Service	Unknown
Monitoring	openITCOCKPIT
Access Methods	NOVA API, Web Interface
Connectivity	Customizable
Cloud-Interface	
Provisioning	Web UI, NOVA API
Cloud Integration	Cloud-init, openstack heat
Networking	Web console, API
MiCADO Integration	NO
Storage	
Interfaces	Cinder (block), S3 (object), CephFS
Image Format	QCOW, RAW
SSD Capacity	-
HDD Capacity	2TB
Quota	None (Can be increased by support on request)
Compute	
CPU (GHz/core)	Not known
CPU Quota	Can be increased by support on request
RAM (GB/VM)	256GB
RAM Quota	Can be increased by support on request
VM Quota	Can be increased by support on request
Linux Provision Time	~3min
Win. Provision Time	-
Networking	
Internal bandwidth	Not known
External bandwidth	~20MB/s
Inter-VM latency	Not known

AWS Cloud	
General Configuration	
Description	Public Amazon Web Services cloud
Hypervisor	Based on KVM
IaaS Service	Elastic Compute Cloud
Monitoring	CloudWatch
Access Methods	EC2/S3 API, Web Interface
Connectivity	Open, fully customisable
Cloud-Interface	
Provisioning	Web UI, MiCADO, EC2 API
Cloud Integration	cloud-init, OpenStack HEAT, EC2
Networking	Web Console, API
MiCADO Integration	Integrated
Storage	
Interfaces	S3 (object), EBS (block)
Image Format	AMI, OVA, VHD, VMDX, RAW
SSD Capacity	16TB
HDD Capacity	16TB
Quota	None known
Compute	
CPU (GHz/core)	-
CPU Quota	None known
RAM (GB/VM)	-
RAM Quota	None known
VM Quota	None known
Linux Provision Time	Fast (30secs)
Win. Provision Time	-
Networking	
Internal bandwidth	-
External bandwidth	-
Inter-VM latency	1ms